

Effects of antibiotics on biological control agents and their efficacy on rice sheath blight (*R. solani* AG-I.1)

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The biological control of rice diseases with antagonistic microbial organisms has been studied extensively and is considered a promising technology (Mew et al 1993). Many factors have been shown to affect the efficacy of biocontrol agents (BCAs), but there have been few studies on effects of pesticides on disease biocontrol (Zhao et al 1992). Some antibiotics have been reported to be effective against bacterial diseases of crops. It is important to determine whether antibiotic applications in the field affect disease suppression by BCAs. In biocontrol studies, mutation with antibiotics has been exploited to obtain bacterial mutants with acquired or increased antagonism to pathogens (Georgakopoulos et al 1994). Little information has been available on bacterial BCA mutations in relation to biocontrol of diseases in rice systems. The objectives of this study were to (1) analyze the direct effects of different antibiotics on the growth of BCAs, (2) obtain BCA mutants with enhanced biocontrol activity, and (3)

examine the effects of antibiotics on rice sheath blight and BCA function.

To determine the effect of antibiotics on the growth of different bacterial BCAs, four BCA strains, B-916 (*Bacillus subtilis*), P7-14 (*Pseudomonas fluorescens*), P9409 (*P. resinovorans*), and P10353 (*P. malculicola*), were grown on peptone potassium nitrate medium (PPM) containing 0.5–1,000 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of four antibiotics: ampicillin, hygromycin, kanamycin, and rifampicin. The four antibiotics affected growth of the four BCAs quite differently (Table 1). Kanamycin had a profound effect on B-916, P7-14, and P9409, which could not grow at 3 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$, but it did not affect the growth of P10353 at concentrations of more than 250 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$. Rifampicin at the highest concentration used in the experiment (1,000 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) did not influence the growth of P7-14, but the other three bacteria stopped growing at 3 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$. However, apart from that of B-916, the growth of the other three bacteria

was not affected by ampicillin at rather high concentrations (>100 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$).

Some BCAs mutated easily, such as P7-14 and P9409 on hygromycin, P10353 and P9409 on rifampicin, and B-916 on ampicillin. Mutants of these BCAs resistant to 1,000 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of the antibiotics were obtained. In other cases, BCAs were very stable, such as B-916 and P9409 on kanamycin and B-916 on rifampicin.

Cell growth (Table 1), pathogenicity, and antagonistic activity of the mutants were not significantly changed compared with parent bacteria, but the growth of $\text{amp}^{\text{R}}-916$ decreased markedly and antagonistic activity of $\text{hyg}^{\text{R}}-714$ and $\text{hyg}^{\text{R}}-9409$ increased markedly ($P < 0.05$).

The three antibiotics (50 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) reduced sheath blight by 60–80% as measured by area under the disease progress curve (AUDPC). B-916 and P9409 [10⁷ colony-forming units (CFU) mL^{-1}] controlled the disease by more than 75%, whereas P7-14 and P10353 were less effective. When an antibiotic (25 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$)

Table 1. Effect of antibiotics on growth of BCAs and mutants.

Antibiotic	BCA	Highest growth ^a concentration ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$)		Mutant	Mutant growth on ^b		
		BCA	Mutant		PPM	PPM + antibiotic	Wild type on PPM
Ampicillin	B-916	1	1,000	$\text{amp}^{\text{R}}-916$	341 b	243 c	735 a
	P7-14	500	–				
	P 10353	500	–				
	P 9409	250	–				
Hygromycin	B-916	10	100	$\text{hyg}^{\text{R}}-714$	752 a	755 a	767 a
	P 7-14	50	1,000				
	P 10353	250	–				
	P 9409	50	1,000				
Kanamycin	B-916	1	10	$\text{hyg}^{\text{R}}-9409$	596 a	582 a	581 a
	P 7-14	1	250				
	P 10353	500	–				
	P 9409	1	10				
Rifampicin	B-916	0.5	3	$\text{rif}^{\text{R}}-10353$	654 a	633 a	639 a
	P 7-14	500	–				
	P 10353	10	1,000				
	P 9409	1	1,000				
				$\text{rif}^{\text{R}}-9409$	611 a	573 a	581 a

^aBCA growth was considered not affected and mutation was not performed when it could grow at 250 mg mL^{-1} . ^bEach value is the mean of six replicates. Means (number of colonies per plate) in a row with the same letter are not significantly different ($P > 0.05$) by DMRT.

was mixed with a BCA (0.5×10^7 CFU mL⁻¹) sensitive to it, disease suppression was consistently weakened, for example, B-916 + ampicillin, P10353 + rifampicin, and P9409 + rifampicin. When an antibiotic and a tolerant BCA were combined, their efficacy was unchanged or enhanced, as shown by P7-14 + hygromycin and P9409 + hygromycin.

Compared with the parent BCA, biocontrol efficacy of hyg^R-714 and hyg^R-9409 was significantly enhanced ($P < 0.05$) or unchanged in other cases ($P > 0.05$). The combined spray of mutant with its inducer antibiotic markedly improved biocontrol efficiency in some cases, but it was not altered in other cases based on the control effect of the mutant.

In conclusion, antibiotics affected the growth of some BCAs but not others. Some BCAs tolerated high concentrations of antibiotics and thus their growth was not affected. Of the five mutants obtained from the BCAs, two had enhanced antagonistic activity and one had lowered growth capability. No mutant developed pathogenicity to rice plants. The antibiotics alone controlled sheath blight, and BCAs and mutants also controlled the disease effectively. When a BCA or mutant was combined with an antibiotic at half the dosage (0.5×10^7 CFU mL⁻¹ and 25 µg mL⁻¹, respectively), the antibiotic enhanced, weakened, or had no effect on sheath blight control, depending on the compatibility of the BCA and antibiotic.

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Table 2. Comparison of sheath blight severity (lesion area in mm²) difference between BCA and antibiotic treatments.^a

Treatment	Days after treatment					AUDPC
	3	4	5	6	7	
B-916	5.4 c	12.3 c	31.2 c	98.7 c	163.3 c	226.6
Amp ^R -B916	1.0 c	8.0 c	24.7 cd	72.7 c	124.0 c	167.9
Amp. 50	4.3 c	12.3 b	29.7 c	73.7 c	115.3 c	175.5
B-916 + A25	15.3 b	33.4 b	86.7 ab	172.0 b	248.5 b	423.8
Amp ^R -B916 + A25	3.0 c	7.7 c	19.0 d	40.0 d	75.3 d	105.9
Check	22.0 a	72.7 a	145.0 a	262.3 a	363.3 a	672.7
7-14	16.3 a	45.7 b	99.0 ab	124.3 bc	201.7 b	383.3
Hyg ^R -714	14.7 ab	33.7 b	55.3 c	96.7 c	146.5 c	266.3
Hyg. 50	5.3 b	15.7 c	45.7 c	86.7 c	127.7 c	214.6
7-14 + H25	22.0 a	58.3 ab	75.3 bc	135.0 b	191.3 b	375.3
Hyg ^R -714 + H25	8.0 b	21.7 c	53.0 c	89.3 c	130.3 c	227.2
Check	22.0 a	72.7 a	145.0 a	262.3 a	363.3 a	672.7
10353	9.7 b	34.0 b	62.7 b	104.3 b	191.0 c	301.4
Rif ^R -10353	10.3 b	22.7 c	53.0 b	94.3 b	150.0 c	250.2
Rif. 50	5.0 b	17.3 c	55.3 b	89.7 b	158.3 c	244.0
10353 + R25	8.0 b	30.7 b	74.7 b	124.3 b	253.3 b	360.4
Rif ^R -10353 + R25	7.7 b	18.5 c	35.3 c	61.4 c	98.7 d	168.4
Check	22.0 a	72.7 a	145.0 a	262.3 a	363.3 a	672.7
9409	6.5 b	15.7 b	35.3 c	84.7 b	173.5 b	225.7
Hyg ^R -9409	0 c	5.3 c	10.7 d	39.7 c	90.3 c	100.9
0.Hyg. 50	5.3 b	15.7 b	45.7 b	86.7 b	127.7 c	214.6
9409 + H25	1.7 b	8.3 c	23.7 d	35.3 c	68.7 d	102.5
Hyg ^R -9409 + H25	1.3 b	6.4 c	21.3 d	33.3 c	45.7 d	89.5
Check	22.0 a	72.7 a	145.0 a	262.3 a	363.3 a	672.7
9409	6.5 c	15.7 c	35.3 c	84.7 c	173.5 c	225.7
Rif ^R -9409	8.3 bc	20.3 bc	44.7 c	95.0 c	203.7 bc	266.0
Rif. 50	5.0 c	17.3 c	55.3 bc	89.7 c	158.3 c	243.9
9409 + R25	11.7 b	31.3 b	66.0 c	156.3 b	251.0 b	389.9
Rif ^R -9409 + R25	1.3 c	22.4 c	51.3 bc	93.3 c	135.7 c	240.5
Check	22.0 a	72.7 a	145.0 a	262.3 a	363.3 a	672.7

^aEach value is the mean of nine replicates. Means in a column with the same letter are not significantly different ($P > 0.05$) by DMRT. AUDPC values were calculated from the means in each treatment.

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